

MULTI-LEVEL ANALYSIS OF SKIN/STRINGER DEBONDING

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SUMMARY

A multi-level analysis of skin/stiffener debonding is used to perform the design of fuselage of future aircraft during postbuckling. The “pyramid of test” approach is used both for experimental and numerical analysis (see Fig 1). The analysis begins with non-specific element (NASA Specimens), then 7 point-bending tests are performed and the approach is finally validated on real panels of an on-going program at Airbus.

Keywords: Skin/stiffener debonding, Global/local finite element analysis, Fracture mechanic.

INTRODUCTION

The coming generations of aircraft structures will be made of all-composite materials but the traditional design composed of stiffeners, frames and thin skins will be kept. However, the stiffeners of metal structures are riveted whereas composite technology allows the stiffeners and skin to be manufactured together. Stiffened aeronautical structures are intended to allow for postbuckling, thus permitting a lighter structure. Postbuckling is allowed within the flight envelope for metal structures but only beyond limit loads for composite structures. Consequently, only static justification is required. In the postbuckling phase, the appearance of buckles and a redistribution of the forces in the stiffener [1] lead to very localised overstresses at the stiffener/skin interface. Thus, the final failure of these structures may occur by stringer debonding between stiffener flanges and the skin of the fuselage [2]. Li et al [3] define an understanding of this phenomenon as the crucial link for the design of composite structure airframes. However, the scales at which debonding and postbuckling occur are very different: of the order of 100 mm for buckles and of the order of 0.1 mm for debonding. The analysis presented here forms part of a multi-level approach, details of which can be found in [4]. It includes experiment and computer simulation and is based on a "pyramid of tests" methodology (Figure 1). The base of the pyramid is a purely experimental level concerning interface characterisation tests for a given material. This part, almost classical (DCB, MMB, ENF tests) will not be presented in this paper [4]. The second level uses non-specific test pieces, i.e. specimens that are representative of a technology (e.g. co-cured or bonded assemblies) but independent of any particular programme or aircraft zone. This type of specimen was used to analyse the influence of local

geometries and environmental effects on the debonding behaviour and to validate a computing methodology [5].

Figure 1: Multi-level analysis of skin-stringer debonding.

At the panel level, tests are usually done on panels having sizes of the order of a metre. The loads are compression, shear exerted through a deformable square and, more rarely, combined compressive/shearing loads with or without internal pressure. However, these tests are complex, costly and often perturbed by the boundary conditions. To correlate the tests, it is often necessary to consider the geometry and exact stiffness of the clamping design and also the initial defects of the specimens [3]. Thus, in order to isolate the phenomena and ensure the reliability of the approach for validating a computing method, it is desirable to perform tests on elements at an intermediate level. The authors used this type of element-level test to study the specificities of omega stringers [6]. Three- or four-point bending tests were used but did not give an optimal simulation of the deformations obtained in postbuckling. So, at this level of analysis, a more specific test is required. Although rarely mentioned in the literature [8], the "7-point" bending test is proposed for validating the choice of computing method at this level and to test the global/local method proposed. The higher level would be to go from

the scale of panels used for certification to computation of the complete aircraft in postbuckling but this step needs methods to be developed that will reduce the computing time required by an order of magnitude.

NON-SPECIFIC ELEMENTS LEVEL

Experimental Analysis.

In this paper, the effects of temperature and wet ageing will not be presented [4-5]. The geometry of the specimens is illustrated in Figure 2. The specimens were manufactured by manually laying up unidirectional, 134 g/m², plies of T700/M21 pre-impregnated laminate. Two ways of manufacturing the flange were studied: co-cured (flange laid up at the same time as the skin) and co-bonded. In the case of co-bonding, the skin was polymerised first and the flange was laid up and placed on the skin with an adhesive film between the two parts. A second polymerisation was thus necessary for these specimens. The local geometry was analysed by varying the thickness of the flange: 1.82 or 2.34 mm (14 or 18 plies) and varying the local shape: straight edges or tapered edges. The behaviour of two types of interface, 0°/0° and 45°/-45°, was analysed.

Figure 2: Specimen overall geometry (straight edges and tapered flanges), unit: mm.

The specimens were subjected to four-point bending as proposed by Krueger et al. [11]. The start of cracking was visually detected using a CCD camera that filmed the side of the specimen, locally painted in white [4-5]. The mechanical behaviour was globally similar for all specimens of the test matrix according to the type of interface. For aeronautical composite structures, the "no-crack growth" principle is used as a design guideline. Thus, the load corresponding to the onset of delamination is used as a criterion for comparing the different configurations proposed. Averages of tests results is shown in Figure 3. Scatter of the results was small, reaching +/- 15 % for the least favourable case (reference case) and +/-2% for the tapered, 0°/0°, co-bonded flange. It was of the order of +/- 5% in general, with lower scatter for the co-bonded specimens. The reference case corresponds to the simplest fabrication (specimen with straight edges) and a 0°/0° interface. When the flange thickness is increased, the crack appears for 16% lower loading. On the other hand, in all cases, the presence of tapering delays the onset of delamination. The greatest increase is + 64% with respect to the reference case. It is thus noteworthy that local design is of paramount importance for the

resistance of the structure. The tapered shape should be recommended despite the difficulty of manufacturing. At the interface, contrary to usual expectations, the 45°/-45° configuration systematically leads to early fracture onset (-38% specimen with straight edges, co-bonded). This can be qualitatively attributed to the fact that local stiffness is modified when the stacking sequence changes. Moreover, material qualification tests have shown that the initial energy release rates are equivalent for both interfaces [4]. The possible advantage to be gained from using the 45°/-45° configuration is one of propagation but, by its very nature, this is in opposition to the "no-crack growth" design principle. As for the choice of manufacturing method, in spite of the cost of the extra polymerisation step, the co-bonded solution clearly has the advantage (+ 56% for specimen with straight edges and + 12% for tapered flanges). The variability among solutions is high: with respect to the reference case, the tapered flange, co-bonded solution gives a gain of + 84%. However, it is noticeable that the advantage of co-bonding over co-curing does not appear to be decisive when environmental effects are included: only +8 % for the case with ageing, - 50°C [4-5].

Figure 3: Comparison of first onset of delamination for specimens at room temperature.

Numerical Analysis

The aims of the numerical study were (i) to confirm the suitability of the Benzeggagh-Kenane criterion proposed by Krueger et al [9] and (ii) to make a comparison at the elementary, non-specific specimen level between the cohesive element and fracture mechanics computing methods found in the literature. The choice made at this level conditions the choice of modelling at the higher level (Figure 1). The Benzeggagh-Kenane criterion in mixed mode I, II and III can be written:

$$G_c = G_1^c + (G_2^c - G_1^c) \cdot \left(\frac{G_2 + G_3}{G_1 + G_2 + G_3} \right)^\eta$$

where the subscript c means “critical” and η is a coupling coefficient related adequate to a fibre/matrix pair. For the carbon fibre/epoxy resin combination it was possible to fix it arbitrarily at 1.5. In the early phases of an aeronautical programme it is necessary to pre-dimension the structures without knowing the final choices of materials or the definitive dimensions. A sensitivity study was therefore carried out a posteriori on the parameter η and did not demonstrate any significant influence. Abaqus software was used. Full details of the models should be found in [4-5]. A first model using cohesive elements was developed (figure 4(a)). Decohesion between the flange and the skin was modelled through a bilinear damage law. The law was implemented over three-quarters of the length of the flange (to allow decohesion at one side only) in cohesive elements of zero thickness. In practice, the use of cohesive elements requires a precise choice of four parameters: the interface pseudo stiffness K_{nn} , the maximum equivalent stress of initiation (Hashin criterion), the critical energy release rate, which is equal to the area under the damage law, and the mesh size. A second model (figure 4(b)), using fracture mechanics and VCCT method, was used. The efficiency of this type of modeling relies on prior knowledge of location of crack initiation, which is the case here, and on the hypothesis of non-perturbation caused by the presence of an initial crack. The VFA method proposed by Abaqus allows node disconnections in order to model the debonding when the criterion is reached, by using contact elements which also avoids any penetration between the debonded area and the skin. A sensitivity study has been made on the pre-crack length and the mesh size and shows that these parameters have little influence. The size was therefore fixed at 1 mm and the pre-crack at 0.5 mm.

Figure 4: Finite element modeling: (a) cohesive; (b) fracture mechanics.

Globally, the computed stiffness correlates correctly with the tested stiffness up to the debonding phase [4-5]. For the cohesive model, Hashin's criterion is reached very early (around 100 N), which is explained by the typical, very high, local interlaminar stresses. However, from a simulation standpoint, this early non-linearity makes it necessary to reduce the time steps, which greatly increases the computing time (5 hours) for the cohesive method. Since the VCCT method is based on practically the same physics, it is logical to find similar values as cohesive method when the criterion is reached for which computation up to debonding only took 5 minutes. The maximum difference between simulation and test was 9 %, which is acceptable. Both methods showed the same aptitude for predicting the onset of debonding. In terms of propagation, the cohesive elements method was much more stable but neither of the models successfully represented the fibre bridges or the change of interface. However the two methods differed by an order of magnitude in computing time for small-sized problems. Thus, for calculating structures of large dimensions, the cohesive elements method is not

suiting to the industrial problems that arise. In the certification and sizing of composite structures, the "No crack growth" principle is used and, thus, only the onset of delamination is really important. Moreover, in this case as in many others, the position where debonding starts is known, either from previous experience or from tests, and the principal limitation of fracture mechanics is not really a problem in practice.

ELEMENTS LEVEL: SEVEN POINTS BENDING TESTS

Experimental Analysis.

The specimens were flat panels to which a T-shaped stiffener was added in the longitudinal direction [4,7]. The skin and the stringer were made of carbon/epoxy laminate and were co-cured without an adhesive film. The skin was composed of 16 crossed symmetrical plies. The same lay-up was used for the 14 plies composing the L-sections that formed the stringer. The skin/stringer interface was $90^\circ/90^\circ$ and the interface of the stringer ply immediately above was $90^\circ/45^\circ$. A total of 10 specimens were made and tested. The principle of 7-point bending tests is given in figure 5. Five points serve as supports for the skin part of the test piece. The supports used are adjustable and enable hyperstatism and flatness defects of the specimens to be managed. Moreover, each support includes a load sensor. The upper block is mobile and composed of two supports. A displacement sensor (LVDT) is installed on the mobile block so that its displacement can be known accurately. The supports in contact with the specimens are articulated to limit their punching effect during testing. A pre-sizing calculation was performed to position the supports in such a way as to avoid any fracture before debonding. It is possible to simulate different fields of displacement by modifying the position of the movable points. The term chosen for this is symmetrical bending (Figure 6(a)) for the type of buckles obtained in compression and antisymmetrical bending for the type obtained in shear (Figure 6(b)). Half of the 10 specimens were used for symmetrical bending tests and the other half for antisymmetrical bending tests.

Figure 5: Principle of 7-point bending test (symmetrical case).

Globally, the test seems fairly reproducible. The lower middle support took up most of the force imposed by the upper supports. The scatter over 5 tests was limited to 14 %. The behaviour and scatter were of the same type for the antisymmetrical tests, with a

different distribution of forces on the supports. Debonding was detected at the first discontinuity of the force vs. displacement curves. It occurred at the skin/stringer interface or at the interface of the ply immediately above ($90^\circ/45^\circ$ interface) and propagated abruptly. The tests were reproducible but, although the scatter remained limited for the symmetrical tests (14%), it reached 32% for the antisymmetrical tests. Analysis showed that the lowest values and highest values were obtained for the same specimen batches, which appears to indicate that the source of scatter was not test related but should be found in the differences in the fabrication of the specimens.

Figure 6: Symmetrical 7-point bending (a); Antisymmetrical 7-point bending (b).

Numerical Analysis: global/local approach.

A first reference model based on 3D shells was created using the Abaqus software which demonstrated the relevance of Benzeggah-Kenane criterion and fracture Mechanic approach [4,7]. The interest of the global/local method lies in the fact that it dissociates the non-linear model required for the postbuckling computation from the model required for the debonding computation. Local models that are refined but of small size can be used for detailed studies of specific zones and a model can be used as often as necessary at different places on the panel. The principle is based on the use of fields of displacement of a zone likely to undergo debonding, provided by the global model, by reinjecting these displacements at the boundaries of a local model better suited to the debonding analysis. As communication between the two scales only goes in one direction, any change in stiffness due to debonding in the local models will not be taken into account in the global model. In consequence, only the onset of debonding can be analysed by this method. Nevertheless, this approach is consistent with the sizing principle for composite aeronautical structures, which does not tolerate any crack propagation. Moreover, tests at structure level show that failure is generally explosive, suggesting that the debonding phenomenon is unstable and that sizing the onset of debonding should suffice to compute the failure of the structure. Two models were used in accordance with the process described above. The global model is presented in Figure 7. The skin, the flange and the web of the stiffener were modelled using reduced-integration linear plate elements (S4R). The link between the flange and the web of the stiffener was described by rigid links, as was the link between the web of the stiffener and the flange. So the radii between the web and the flange were not modelled. In accordance with the reference model used previously, loading was applied using seven supports, two of which (upper supports) were subjected to imposed displacements to produce the required loading. The global computation was non-linear geometric. The local model comprised a skin part and a flange part. The skin and flange were modelled

by 3D shells of coincident meshes. The displacements coming from the global model were imposed at the boundaries of the local model. The principle of reinjection is given in Figure 11. The boundary nodes of the global model were recreated in the local model at their geometric locations (master nodes). The nodes of the 3D shell elements of a section of the local model (slave nodes) were controlled geometrically by the 5 d.o.f. coming from the nodes of the plate elements following the Kirchhoff-Love hypothesis and via rigid elements. The choice of the size of the local model is studied in [4] on a virtual test patch. The optimum size needed to verify the St Venant assumption is about half a wavelength. Therefore, the problem is more defined by the time needed to build the local model than by the minimum size. If the analysis area is too small, too many local models are needed. The "virtual crack" is 0.5 mm long. The VCCT technique is used to determine the energy release rates and the Benzeggagh-Kenane criterion is applied. The local calculation is non-linear requiring two or three steps.

Figure 7: Global/local methodology.

For the symmetrical case, the computed debonding load was within 7 % of the first fracture load observed in test and within 16 % of the mean fracture load. Considering the high scatter in the test results (about 14 %), this value is perfectly acceptable. For the antisymmetrical case, the computed debonding load was within less than 1% of the minimum debonding load obtained experimentally and within 19 % of the mean of the tests. Considering the high scatter in the test results (32%), this result is acceptable. The modal distribution at the failure load was of the same type for both tests. Mode I was preponderant and the ratio of $G_{II}/(G_I+G_{II})$ was 33% for the symmetrical test and 29% for the antisymmetrical test. Thus, the global/local methodology was validated at this level.

PANEL LEVEL

Experimental Analysis.

Two tests were analysed but in this paper only the shear one will be presented. The tests are not specific to this study but form part of the certification process for a current Airbus programme. Therefore, only the general methodology of the tests and numerical approach are given here. The aim is to validate the approach for a higher level and in an operational context. The problem of correlating with structural tests at these scales will not be presented here since it is long and complex and involves certain data that cannot

be disclosed but the essential points can be found in [4]. The two stiffened panels used in the programme were composed of a panel and three omega stringers made of carbon/epoxy laminate. The panels were co-cured. The shear test and the failure mode are described figure 8. The shear test was carried out using a deformable square. Shearing failure was explosive and was caused by the debonding of the central stiffener (Figure 8). Buckling was detected by the loss of linearity of the gauges and by image correlation at 360 kN. The breaking load was 425 kN.

Figure 8: Shear test with a deformable square and failure mode: stringer debonding.

Numerical Analysis.

The shear global model is shown in Figure 8. To properly represent the postbuckling behaviour, it was necessary to represent the reinforcing plies, the frame itself (in volume elements) and the various attachment points. Rotation of the different parts of the frame was allowed by controlling the local contacts. The model has 7 million degrees of freedom. The model gave acceptable correlation with the test and the details in terms of loads/displacements and local strains given by the gauges can be found in [4]. The global/local approach presented and validated by the 7-point bending test was applied to both cases (Figure 9). The main modification was that the omega shape of the stringers made necessary the study of the debonding on both sides of the flange. To respect the St Venant hypothesis and thus avoid the boundary conditions at the edges of the local model perturbing the results, pieces of skin and stiffener web were modelled. The size of the local model was about a quarter of the length of the panel, which allowed the structure to be covered with a good compromise between computing time and accuracy [4]. The local model was built up of 3D shells and the radius between the flange and the web of the stringer was modelled. The resin corners could vary from one stringer to another. It was therefore decided not to model them and to place the virtual crack at the flange/web radius (Figure 9). This hypothesis is very conservative [6]. The calculated buckling load was 338 kN, as compared with the 360kN obtained experimentally. The error on the buckling load is thus about 10 %, which is acceptable considering the complexity of the test. After scanning the structure, the critical site was indeed found in the centre of the panel at the free edge of the flange of the central stringer, at the level of the largest buckle. Debonding was reached at the critical site for 469 KN, the error being 9.4 % with respect to the test result (425 KN). This error, which is reasonable considering the complexity of the test could be due to the non-linear behaviour of the panel which is not perfectly represented in spite of the very refined modelling used. Moreover, the value of the energy release in mode III is not identical to that of mode II although it is usual to make the approximation. But, in this case it appears that mode III is the main mode before failure which was unexpected.

Figure 9: Shear finite element model and global/local model for omega stringers.

CONCLUSIONS

A multilevel analysis of stiffener debonding, both experimental numerical was proposed and validated. From a numerical point of view, a global/local approach was applied and enabled calculation of the loads corresponding to local debonding. At this stage, the mixed Benzeggagh-Kenane criterion was validated together with the computing method. Moreover, in a certification programme, the methodology was applied to stiffened panels. The prediction of debonding at this scale is consistent with the tests. If the mass of composite structures is to be optimized, it would be desirable to lower the threshold for postbuckling below the limit loads. However, it would then become necessary to use the same multi-level approach for fatigue.

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